

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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KIRISH SO‘ZI

HURMATLI ANJUMAN ISHTIROKCHILARI, MEHMONLAR, HAMKASBLAR, AZIZ TALABALAR!

Sizlarni Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot instituti tomonidan tashkil etilayotgan mazkur Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumanida qutlashdan mamnunmiz.

Qadrli anjuman ishtirokchilari, bugun biz mamlakatimizda biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash va iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish masalalari bo‘yicha amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar, mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo‘llari, hamda bu yo‘nalishdagi xorijiy tajribalarni muhokama qilish uchun to‘plandik.

Habaringiz bor, Prezidentimiz tomonidan 2024-yilni O‘zbekistonda “Yoshlar va biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash yili”, deb e‘lon qilinganida, inson qadrini ulug‘lash va aholimiz manfaatlarini ta‘minlash uchun kuchli iqtisodiyot barpo etish asosiy vazifalarimizdan biri ekanligi ta‘kidlangan edi.

Shunga ko‘ra, joriy yilda iqtisodiyotimizga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishga, tadbirkorlik va xususiy mulk uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratishga, ilm-fan, innovatsiya, IT kabi sohalarni, “yashil” va raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga alohida e‘tibor qaratilmoqda.

Chunki, barqaror va kuchli iqtisodiyot nafaqat iqtisodiyot subyektlari uchun, balki jamiyatimizning kelajagi va farovonligi uchun ham juda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Hozirgi kunda, bizning jamiyatimiz - raqamli transformatsiya davriga qadam qo‘ydi. Raqamlashtirish jarayoni - biznes jarayonlaridan tortib, davlat xizmatlariga qadar ko‘plab sohalarni qamrab olmoqda.

Albatta bunday o‘zgarishlar, texnologik taraqqiyotga hamohang ravishda, qo‘shimcha imkoniyatlarni ochishga va rivojlanishning yangi strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishga keng imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda.

Lekin shu bilan bir qatorda, iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish va bunday sharoitda biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida, o‘ziga xos muammolar va turli savollar ham yuzaga kelmoqda.

Bunday masalalarni o‘rganib, uning yechimlarini topish uchun Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot institutining professor-o‘qituvchilari tomonidan ham turli ilmiy tadqiqotlarni olib borish yo‘lga qo‘yilgan. Ularning tadqiqotlari natijalaridan - o‘quv jarayonlarida, ta‘lim sifatini oshirish maqsadlarida, keng foydalaniladi.

Bu o‘z navbatida, institutda menejment, iqtisodiyot va axborot texnologiyalari sohasida tayyorlanadigan malakali mutaxassislarining nafaqat nazariy bilimlarini, balki amaliy ko‘nikmalarini ham oshirishga hizmat qiladi.

Bundan tashqari, institutda innovatsion dasturlar va loyihalar orqali talabalarni yangi texnologiyalar bilan tanishtirish, ularda raqamli iqtisodiyot va global biznes muhitida raqobatbardosh bo‘lish uchun zarur bo‘lgan ko‘nikmalarni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Bugungi anjumanda, biz raqamlashtirish va biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida uchraydigan muammolarni chuqur o‘rganishni va ilmiy asoslangan yechimlarni izlashni o‘z oldimizga maqsad qilib qo‘yganmiz.

Shu bilan birga, asosiy anjuman va sho‘ba yig‘ilishlarida mazkur masalalar bo‘yicha xorijiy tajribalarni ham tahlil qilish orqali, biz qanday yechimlar topishimiz mumkinligini muhokama qilamiz.

Bugun sizlarning e‘tiboringizga taqdim etiladigan taqdimotlar va fikrlar - bizni zamonaviy iqtisodiyotning yangi talablariga mos keladigan biznes modellarni yaratishga ilhomlantiradi.

Maqsadimiz – bu kabi ilmiy-amaliy uchrashuvlar orqali ilm ahlini va biznes vakillarini bir joyda jamlab, biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini hamda iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish jarayonlarini yanada takomillashtirish bo‘yicha asoslangan takliflar va amaliy tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqishga imkoniyatlar yaratishdan iboratdir.

Biz bu jarayonda, o‘z tajribamizni almashish va birgalikda muammolarni hal qilish uchun yangi g‘oyalarni kashf etishni maqsad qilamiz.

Umid qilamanki, anjumanimiz samarali va foydali bo‘ladi.

Har biringizning ishtirokingiz va hissangiz bu jarayonda juda muhim.

Keling, birgalikda yangiliklarga ochiq bo‘lib, innovatsion yechimlarni izlaylik!

Bugungi anjuman ishiga va unda ishtirok etayotgan barcha ishtirokchilarning ilmiy-ijodiy faoliyatlariga ulkan muvaffaqiyatlar tilaymiz!

**Axmedov Xojiakbarxon Dilshatovich,
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3-SHO‘BA. **MOLIYA VA SOLIQ SOHASIDAGI MUAMMOLAR,** **YECHIMLAR VA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR**

INITIAL RESEARCH: ARE THE CURRENT RESEARCHED EARLY WARNING INDICATORS SIGNIFICANT IN IDENTIFYING BANKING CRISES?

Berdiyev Bekzod Shoymardonovich,

Senior Teacher, Department of "Management, Economics and Humanitarian" subjects
Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent

Masharipov Sarvar Matkarimovich

Chief Head of Credit Departments I&II, JSC "KDB Bank Uzbekistan"

Berdiyev Jahongir Shaymardon o'g'li

Risk Manager, JSC "KDB Bank Uzbekistan"

Abstract: This paper proposes an empirical methodology to evaluate the current leading Early Warning Indicators (EWIs) of banking indicators and proposes any additional indicators that should be used by policymakers to forecast any crises within the banking industry. For this purpose, using a pooled logistic regression model to illustrate the accuracy of the five chosen indicators of a banking crises is recommended.

Key words: Early Warning Indicators (EWIs), Banking Crises, pooled logistic model.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola bank ko'rsatkichlarining joriy etakchi erta ogohlantirish ko'rsatkichlarini (EOK) baholash uchun empirik metodologiyani hamda davlat tomonidan bank sohasida har qanday inqirozni bashorat qilish uchun ishlatilishi kerak bo'lgan har qanday qo'shimcha ko'rsatkichlarni taklif qiladi. Shu maqsadda tanlangan beshta bank inqirozi ko'rsatkichlarining to'g'riligini tasvirlash uchun birlashtirilgan logistik regressiya modelidan foydalanish tavsiya etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: erta ogohlantirish ko'rsatkichlari (EWI), bank inqirozlari, qo'shma logistika modeli.

Аннотация: В данной статье предлагается эмпирическая методология оценки текущих ведущих индикаторов раннего предупреждения (ИРП) банковских индикаторов и предлагаются любые дополнительные индикаторы, которые должны использоваться государствами для прогнозирования любых кризисов в банковской отрасли. Для этой цели рекомендуется использовать объединенную модель логистической регрессии для иллюстрации точности пяти выбранных индикаторов банковского кризиса.

Ключевые слова: индикаторы раннего предупреждения (EWI), банковские кризисы, объединенная логистическая модель.

INTRODUCTION

Early Warning Indicators (EWIs) are important tactics policymakers and economic forecasters use to assess the vulnerability of economic conditions to potential severe financial crises. EWIs are not only different for emerging and advanced economies, but they are also specific for different types of financial crises. The volatility of domestic currency tends to signal the possibility of a currency crisis, the debt to GDP ratio or the value of international debt on the balance payments accounts signal debt crises and extreme changes in interest rates and property prices are indicators of banking crises; so, policymakers have a wide variety of indicators in their disposal to accurately signal different types of financial crises and protect the domestic economy.

Examples of EWIs are mainly financial factors which include credit-to-GDP gaps or national property prices for advanced economies. These indicators are regularly monitored across the years, any volatility in the cyclical

pattern of the indicators, e.g., an unexpected rise or fall in the overall property prices, can highlight any build-up of hidden problems within a financial sector that will eventually lead to crises if not managed. Usually if the indicators are stable in the long-term, EWIs tend to signal a financial crisis three years prior to the crisis in order to provide policymakers with the opportunity to implement effective policies in the economy to avoid or reduce the consequences of a crisis within the domestic banking sector.

EWIs were well researched before the Great Financial Crisis (GFC) by authors like Dermirgüç-Kunt and Detergiache or Calvo. There were numerous indicators that were highly acknowledged as significant indicators of financial crises, yet these indicators were mismanaged and undetected by policymakers. The banking crises in 1973 and 2008 were similar, they were both triggered by deregulation in the banking sector and extensive growth in the property market, that soon crashed and led to big banks' experiencing issues with liquidity; (Lambert, 2008). So, there were obvious indicators that should have been detected after the 1975 crisis and successfully implemented in the economy to avoid the banking crisis in 2008. So, more research needs to be carried out on EWIs or policymakers need to spend more time and resources on implementing specific indicators to protect the economy from future banking crisis.

There is a strong necessity to focus on the early warning indicators of a banking crisis, assessing the significance of the already well-established indicators and study the possibilities of their application for the case of Uzbekistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There has been extensive research on the leading early indicators of banking crisis, evaluating the developments leading up to a banking crisis and the post-crisis consequences of false alarms. This section evaluates past papers focused on analysing the leading indicators of banking crises and the significance and validity of financial indicators such as the national debt to GDP ratio to track vulnerabilities of banking crises. For instance, Gavin and Hausman (1996) suggest that credit growth is a highly significant indicator of vulnerabilities in the banking system, as crises tend to be an after-effect of excessive borrowing in the inter-bank systems, as proven in the Great Financial Crisis (GFC) in 2007-09.

Main early warning indicator that are proven to be significant early warning indicators of banking crisis are the debt service ratio (DSR), credit-to-GDP gap, loans-to-deposit ratio and property prices. Laina, Nyholm and Sarlin (2015) use univariate signal extraction and multivariate logit analysis to assess the usefulness of macro-financial indicators, their various transformations over crises and optimal lead horizons. Their main conclusion is that the most successful indicators of systematic banking crises in a panel of 11 EU countries, with a main focus on Finland, are the growth rates of loans to deposits and house prices. The results showed that the growth in the loans to deposits ratio peaked at 7% and 13% two years prior to the 2008 Q3 crisis and 1991 Q3 banking crises, but then decelerates to become negative at the beginning of the crises and reach -1% and -10% three years after the crises. The growth rate in real house prices saw extreme movements compared to the average growth rate during the 1991 Q3 banking crisis for the rest of the EU countries. Real house prices grew over 30% before the crisis, then turned negative almost two years before and dropped by 20% at the start of the crisis. Not only does this paper, use a mixture of univariate and multivariate models to assess the usefulness of early warning indicators, it also investigates cross correlations between different lags of the indicators and the crisis dummy. The authors plot of the cross correlation of the indicators alongside a crisis dummy and observe that the growth rate of house prices variable lagged by three years is most correlated with crisis occurrences and the growth rate of level of loans to deposits ratio lagged by two years is just correlated with the onset of a crisis.

However besides from real growth of GDP, Laina et al (2015) do not find much evidence that macroeconomic variables such as inflation and current account deficits, are good early warning indicators of a banking crisis. Which contradict the claims of past highly critically reviewed papers and the criteria policymakers use to implement effective early warning models to track banking crises. In addition, the authors of this paper analysed that for a shorter lead time window before a crisis, trend deviations of the loan stock variables are better explanatory variables than the growth rates. Also, this paper does not attempt to prove evidence on the predictability of overall systemic banking crises as the sample as relied heavily on European countries especially Finland, that have different banking systems and regulation compared to other countries, so the findings of house prices and loan to deposit ratios as leading indicators of banking crises may not be relatable to worldwide banking systems.

Annual financial indicators such as the inflation rate are also found to be significant indicators of banking crises. An empirical study implemented by Dermirgüç-Kunt and Detergiache (1997) using evidence from developing and developed countries observed that banking crises are a result of a weak macroeconomic environment characterised by slow GDP growth, high inflation, and high real interest rates. An increase in short-term interests causes deteriorations to bank balance sheets and problems in the inter-bank lending system.

In addition, Hardy and Pazarbasioglu (1999) also statistically analysed that a rise followed by a sharp fall in inflation is the most reliable early indicator of an impending banking crisis. And real interest rates tend to start increasing in the years before a banking crisis. Compared to the real exchange rate which is proven to appreciate before the banking crisis.

These papers have not only emphasized the importance of the rate of interest and inflation as significant early warning indicators of banking crises, but they have also provided clear signals to government authorities on how they should implement fiscal and monetary policies in the economy to reduce the vulnerability of banking systems to financial shocks. A paper by Cheang (2005) proved that a signalling based EWS model produced statistically significant in-sample forecasts, around 70% of the indicators signalled deterioration in macroeconomic fundamentals two years prior the Asian Financial Crisis for Thailand and the Philippines.

Other papers have highlighted the importance of additional financial indicators that should be considered to avoid a banking crisis in the future. Frankel and Saravelos (2010) suggest that central bank international reserves and real exchange rate overvaluation are top two leading indicators of a banking crisis. They conduct bivariate regressions with income level as a control variable and found that coefficients on reserves and past appreciation are statistically significant at the 5% significance level across more than half of the regressions performed and are therefore significant leading early warning indicators of banking crises across different countries.

However, a main criticism of Frankel and Saravelos's (2010) paper is that when the multivariate model is re-estimated with reserves measured in terms of short-term or external debt and M2, the coefficient on reserves relative to GDP loses significance. Therefore, the statistical analysis in this paper, proposing that international reserves is a leading indicator of banking crises may not be a valid across all horizons and successfully signal a banking crisis in a banking sector where reserves are long term and highly liquid. The methodology in this paper is based solely on evidence from the 2008-09 global crisis, where the financial conditions before a crisis were unusual such as lack of regulation and the mismanagement of funds in the international banking industry. Since then, new financial requirements have been implemented into the banking industry. The Financial Policy Committee was given overall responsibility for financial regulation in the UK from 2013 and in 2010, a bank levy was introduced to sustain suitable bank balance sheets. Thereby, altering the conditions of banking operations used in this paper to predict a crisis, reducing the validity and generalisation of findings in this research paper to future banking crises.

A review of past research on early warning indicators of a banking crisis has established that there are different indicators for advanced and emerging economies. Chen and Svirydzenka (2021) used data from 59 advanced and emerging economies and found that equity prices and output gap are the best leading indicators in advanced economies, for emerging economies, these are equity and property prices and credit gaps. Aggregating all these indicators signals financial crises many years before a crisis. However, there is inefficient research on the significance of early warning indicators for banking crises for emerging economies, emerging economies often exhibit different institutional frameworks, regulations and economic structures compared to advanced economies. This imposes methodological challenges in developing generalised EWIs that are applicable across diverse emerging markets. Also in emerging economies, policymakers often have limited resources and face multiple economic and financial instabilities. As a result, their focus may be on immediate policy responses rather than long-term research on EWIs. Contributing to an even distribution of research papers on EWIs for banking crises between developed and developing countries. Therefore, in this paper I will focus on evaluating the significance of current leading EWIs of banking crises with data sample focused solely on advanced developed countries and try to propose the best methodology for further evaluation.

METHODOLOGY

To build upon on the paper, "Early warning indicators of banking crises: expanding the family" by Aldasoro, Borio and Drehmann (2018), and provide a more in-depth analysis of early warning indicators for systematic banking crises, extracting the credit-to-GDP gap, property prices and total DSR variables from the base paper and including additional variables such as the rate of inflation and loans-to-deposits ratio (LDR) could be a good practice.

It is time-consuming and difficult to manage a large data containing all the indicators from the base paper and the two additional indicators, so using three indicators from the base paper is feasible. The credit-to-GDP gap, property prices and total DSR are already established by past papers to be the most significant and leading EWIs of banking crises, whereas the other indicators from the base paper, the foreign currency to GDP ratio or the cross-border claims to GDP ratio are more likely to signal currency and debt crises. Limiting the number of indicators will also make it easier to compare the additional indicators to the indicators from the base paper, as I will be able to use more statistical estimates and methods to critically analyse if the additional

indicators are significant EWIs of banking crises.

The rate of inflation is referred to as the general rise in the overall price level with a corresponding fall in the value of the domestic currency. When the rate of inflation increases unexpectedly, the operational costs of banks have increased more compared to their total income as it now costs more to hold money in the reserves, increasing their cost-to-income ratio and their vulnerability to financial shocks. In addition, to the rising operational costs, during periods of high inflation, depositors may divert their money away from banks to assets to offset the rising costs of living, further reducing the bank reserves of domestic banks and exposing them to liquidity issues and might result in a systematic banking crisis; (Mosk and Welz, 2022). Supporting the claim that the rate of inflation is a useful indicator of banking crises. The effectiveness of the inflation rate as an EWI of banking crisis is also proven by past papers by Dermirgüç-Kunt and Detergiache (1997) and Hardy and Pazarbasioglu (1999) outlined before in the literature review. And by real-time data, when two years prior to the GFC the inflation rate was already above the target of 2% and increased by 4.6% from 2005-2007; (WorldData, 2022).

The loan-to-deposit ratio (LDR) is used to assess a bank's liquidity by comparing a bank's total loans to its total deposits, which is typically between 80% to 90% for banks. If the LDR is too high, banks are lending out more money to creditors than they have in bank reserves, so in times of crises they may not have enough liquidity to cover any expected fund requirements. Resulting in national bank runs and systematic shocks within the banking system. If the LDR is too low, banks are earning little or no revenue on their balance sheets and will therefore have high opportunity costs that may not be manageable in the long run, increasing the possibility of a bank failure and a domestic banking crisis. The usefulness of LDR as an indicator of a banking crisis is proven by the research paper by Laina et al (2015), results showed that the growth rates in the loans to deposits ratio were volatile before the 1991 and 2008 banking crises.

Data Recommendations

It is feasible to collect most of the data from the BIS database, the Bank of International Settlements online platform is where one can find the base paper by Aldasoro, Borio and Drehmann (2018) and provides up-to-date highly accurate data on monetary and financial stability factors. Using quarterly data is recommended as policymakers implement policies according to quarterly economic data; and EWIs tend to signal banking crisis on a quarterly basis.

The time period that to cover could be from 1980 to 2019, which covers severe banking crises such as worldwide systematic banking crises in the mid-1980s to early 1990s and the GFC banking crisis from 2007 to 2009. And the sample size for each indicators includes various developed countries, e.g., the United Kingdom or Germany. However, some of the data is not available from 1980 to 2019, most of the data samples for the indicators are only accessible from 1991 or 1995; and some samples for the indicators have more countries. So, some results may not be generalisable to all economic circumstances.

Using data from 2019 onwards is not effective as the last four years does not provide additional banking crises episodes. And the covariates would suffer from strong breaks during the coronavirus pandemic in 2020. If one accounts for these structural breaks in the data sample, the data sample will have a skewed distribution and the results might be heavily dependent on these methodological issues, resulting in irrelevant results for the significance of early warning indicators of banking crises.

The credit-to-GDP gap is defined as the difference between the ratio of total non-financial sector credit-to-GDP and its trend based on a one-sided Hodrick-Prescott (HP) filter with a smoothing parameter equal to 400,000. The data sample used in this paper for this indicator is from 1980-Q1 to 2019-Q4, containing 27 countries and 25 banking crises. The property price gap is the deviation of the inflation-adjusted property prices from a trend constructed using the same parameters as the credit-to-GDP gap. The data sample for the property price gap is also from 1980-Q1 to 2019-Q4, containing 19 contains and 20 banking crises.

By transforming the dataset from a ratio to a gap, it ensures that the deviation from the trend is equal to 0, so there are no cyclical trends, and the benchmark is equal to 0 in all the countries. So, the indicators are comparable between countries and it is clear that the differences in the performance are not based on any methodological issues.

The total DSR is estimated using information from debt maturities, interest rates and outstanding debt stocks. The data sample is from 1999-Q1 to 2019-Q4, containing 17 countries and 17 banking crises.

It is easy to use the World Bank online database to collect data for the inflation rates of different developed countries. The inflation rates are measured in terms of the official core consumer price index are also de-trended using the HP filter to that deviation from the mean of the sample size is equal to 0 and the findings are comparable to each country. The dataset is from 1980-Q1 to 2019-Q4, containing 23 countries and 23 banking crises.

Figure 1. Data sample:

TABLE A1	Credit-to-GDP Gap	Total DSR	Property Price Gap	Loans-to-Deposit Gap	Inflation Rate
Time Period:	1980 Q1 to 2019 Q4	1991 Q1 to 2019 Q4	1980 Q1 to 2019 Q4	2000 Q1 to 2019 Q4	1980 Q1 to 2019 Q4
Countries:	(27) Austria, Australia, Belgium, Canada, Switzerland, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, India, Italy, Japan, Korea, Malaysia, Netherlands, Norway, New Zealand, Portugal, Sweden, Singapore, Thailand, United States.	(17) Australia, Belgium, Canada, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Italy, Japan, Korea, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Sweden, United States.	(19) Australia, Belgium, Canada, Switzerland, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Ireland, India, Italy, Japan, Korea, Netherlands, Norway, New Zealand, Sweden, United States.	(12) Austria, Belgium, Germany, Spain, Finland, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Portugal.	(23) Austria, Australia, Belgium, Canada, Switzerland, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Luxembourg, Mexico, Netherlands, New Zealand, Portugal, Sweden, United States.
No of banking crises:	25	17	20	11	23

And finally, there is an easy access that could be acquired to get the data for the loan-to-deposit ratios from the European Central Bank (ECB) online database. Using the HP filter, one can detrend the data and transform the ratio to a gap to ensure comparability between all the countries in the sample. The dataset is from 2000-Q1 to 2019-Q4, containing 12 countries and 11 banking crises.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This paper proposes the empirical methodology to evaluate the current leading early warning indicators of banking indicators and proposes any additional indicators that should be used by policymakers to forecast any crises within the banking industry, since there is a strong necessity to focus on the early warning indicators of a banking crisis, assessing the significance of the already well-established indicators and study the possibilities of their application for the case of Uzbekistan.

There are further areas to research in the topic of early warning indicators of banking crises, there is the possibility of a fourth generation to capture the dynamic nature of banking crises. And the inclusion of contagion indexes to enhance the efficiency of existing EWIs, instead of using a dummy index subject to post-crisis bias in the model. The fourth-generation model aims to identify the characteristics of the institutional environment that are the basis for the build-up of macroeconomic imbalances, which result in a banking crisis. Incorporating variables such as regulatory framework or protection of shareholders helps to identify financial imbalances in the banking industry prior to a banking crisis. There are control variables reflecting the structure of the banking sector and the broader institutional and governance environment into their multivariate cross-sectional analysis and some evidence that countries with higher quality financial sector policies can contain the effects of macroeconomic pressures and vulnerabilities of the banking system.

There is a lack of research on banking regulations and supervision practices being leading indicators of banking crises. One of the main causes of the GFC in 2008, especially in the UK, was a mismanagement of funds by banking authorities and unsupervised extensively high excessive borrowing in the inter-banking community so further analysis on the potential significant indicators will improve the accuracy of the early warning models in signalling true banking crises, which should be highly considered as we are still seeing damaging banking crises in the modern century.

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